

EFFICIENT METHODS THAT ENSURE THE SALE OF THE MOUNTAIN PRODUCT, THROUGH VISUAL ELEMENTS

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Abstract

One of the current difficulties faced by people who want to sell the mountain product is represented by the small number of local brands, which are registered and promoted. More than that, the promotion is often focused on attending to fairs (or other similar events), the support coming primarily from the community, but also from the experts in the field. However, it would be possible to increase the sales of the mountain product if we took into consideration aspects such as the profile of the current buyer, persons who can have access to the mountain product online, who have a high standard of living and want a healthy, organic diet. To get to this type of buyer, it is very important to pay attention to the visual elements, to the graphics that we find on the packaging of the mountain product, and it is desirable that the graphic is as attractive as possible. This paper includes some graphic design elements essential for the desired appearance of the packaging and case studies.

***Keywords:** mountain product, promotion, mountain area, rural development, buyer profile*

INTRODUCTION

In order to understand which are the current difficulties but also the possible solutions regarding the sale of the mountain product (through visual elements), we must first have a clear picture of its definition. "**Mountain product**" means the product which is intended for human consumption, in which case we can include here the raw materials but also the feed for farm animals are coming mainly from the mountain area, and also the processed products, if the processing takes also place in the mountain area.

The label "Mountain product" is an optional mention, which can be attributed to:

1. Products of animal origin

(1) Products obtained from animals which live in mountain areas and which are processed here.

(2) Products obtained from animals raised for at least the last two thirds of their life in mountain areas, if the products are processed in these areas.

(3) Products obtained from transhumant animals, raised for at least a quarter of their lives in transhumance and which grazed on pastures in the mountain area.

2. Bee products, if the bees collected nectar and pollen only from mountainous areas.

3. Products of vegetable origin, only if the plants are grown in mountainous areas.

Processing operations outside mountain areas

The slaughter of the animals and the cutting and boning of carcasses may take place outside mountain areas, provided that the distance from the mountain area in question does not exceed 30 km. (ANZM - issues the decision to grant the right to use the optional quality mention "mountain product", according to Order no. 52/2017 with subsequent amendments and completions.)

However, similar to the case of other products, the mountain ones face difficulties. First

of all, there is a small number of local brands registered and promoted, so they may seem almost insignificant on the market. Then, the associative environment is poorly represented in the mountain area, and the setup is low (when it comes to agricultural products and non-agricultural entrepreneurs). There is no coherent system of assistance, advice and consultancy for the rural development, and the certified traditional products are reduced in number, compared to the potential of the area. Another element that does not help is the fact that the prices of agricultural products are not competitive, and the organic farming is poorly developed, compared to the potential of the area.

For a better image of the mountain product, it is necessary to have ways of protection and intelligent, sustainable and inclusive development of the mountain area, by highlighting the material and human resources. It can also be about raising the standard of living, but also visiting some trade areas where the standard of living is already high. The stabilization of the population in rural mountain areas is a very important, difficult element that, in recent years, Romania has constantly faced. Moreover, in order to preserve the charm of the mountain product, it is necessary to maintain the cultural identity and the increase of the economic power at local and national level, while maintaining the ecological balance and the protection of the natural environment.

When it comes to the manner in which we can present the rural mountain product, it is necessary to take into account the following aspects:

- The quality of the products is associated with that of the territories;
- The quality of the mountain products is connected to the management of production in balance with the conditions and natural local mountain resources;
- The production and assembly of product processing stages are located in mountainous areas and are "linked" to the territory;
- A mountain product can be marketed at local, regional, national and European level.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In conducting this research I used the following methods: documentary study, theoretical analysis, information synthesis and empirical study. Advertising ensures the connection between the products and the target audience. For this information to be effective, it must express the solution of a need that people have, in a way that can be passed on and combined with the rivalry.

Each brand creates its advertising campaign according to the desire of the target audience, the product it offers, the space in which it can take place, and, of course, depending on the budget. The behaviour of the consumer represents "the totality of individual or group decision-making acts directly related to the acquisition and use of goods and services, in order to meet current or future needs, including decision-making processes that precede and determine these acts" (Engelet. al. 1995).

The audience must be chosen according to the message we send. Are we addressing both women and men? What is the proper age range for our service and how many people do we want our message to reach? Social networks set filters based on each user's appreciation, which is why we can set certain keywords that define our campaign to make sure it reaches people with the same preferences. The message that the campaign sends in the online environment must be short, in order to be understood by all those included in the previously selected audience, and it has to have a short presentation of the benefits gained by choosing the products.

Due to the current interests for environmental conservation and extension of lifetime, young people (especially) are looking for food made as fair and healthy as possible and sometimes the price is not even a decisive factor. Moreover, if the focus is on the buyer who does most of the shopping online, this person can live in areas where the standard of living is high, his interest could be to choose the best product (from a qualitative point of view), and for him it would not be necessary to go to the supermarket, regardless of costs. Another important aspect of the consumer customer is the fact that he wants to turn a product into a real experience. For example, the mountain product, if purchased by the buyer, can be offered as a souvenir (after visiting an area, as a symbol of living in this area). More than that, you can create experiences in which the mountain product is included. At the moment, an idea that is practiced in the Sibiu area is to offer the accommodation accompanied by a tour of the area, tourists traveling a number of kilometers by bike, admiring the landscapes, but having the possibility to stop at the local producers in order to taste and purchase food (which is used at the picnic after that, this experience being announced at the beginning of the tour).

For a correct advertising, it is necessary that all the elements be presented in a way that everyone can understand. The customer is interested about the manufacturer brand, the product / service, a short description of it, details on dimensions, materials and techniques.

The advertising is divided into two main categories: online and offline.

The offline environment integrates tangible advertising services, which can be printed on paper / cardboard with different textures, plastic, wood, metal or even textiles. This category includes the following products: business cards, posters, packaging, banners, roll-ups, inscribed promotional items. The business card is a dispensable business accessory. This cardboard rectangle serves as a means of written and graphic communication and, in the same time, it represents the person in front of customers, collaborators and present and future business partners. The business card contains the following information:

- the name, the company's logo and maybe its slogan;
- the person's name and surname;
- the profession, usually written in characters smaller than the name;
- the contact data: address, phone number, e-mail, site, etc.

The business card represents the person, and, at the same time, the company for which he works. In order for the message sent by it to be the desired one, all the elements contained must match. Graphics has an important role in the correct transmission of the message, which is why it is preferably for it to be simple and clear. The colors must match the ones in the logo in order not to overcrowd the image. The text must be legible, the business card is large enough to use fonts of reasonable size. It is recommended the usage of a good quality cardboard, as the tactile sense contributes to the understanding of the message sent. The business card must determine the other speaker to keep it.

The banner and the Roll-up are advertising items of large size, printed on canvas or plastic. The banner is used outdoors, and it is placed on different buildings or above the streets, while the roll-up is used mostly indoors. Their size allows for the messages to be seen from a greater distance and by a larger number of people. Communication is achieved through text, image and the free space between them.

The packaging is a material (paper, cardboard, plastic, etc.) in which something is packaged in order to be stored or transported. The packaging contains, protects, preserves, transports, informs and sells. It contains the name of the company, the logo, details about the product it contains. Even if its basic purpose is to protect the product, it can easily be used as an advertising item. Packagings are classified according to several criteria, which are frequently used in practice:

- a. by the way of usage: single use; reusable (returnable);
- b. by the material used in the packaging: paper and cardboard packaging; glass packaging; metal packaging; plastic packaging; wooden packaging, wooden substitutes and braids; textile packaging; packaging made of complex materials.
- c. by the manufacturing system: fixed packaging; removable packaging; foldable packaging.
- d. by the type: envelopes; bags; placement; daily; boxes; bottles; jars.
- e. by the field of use: transport packaging; sales and presentation packaging.
- f. by the specifics of the packaged product: food packaging; packaging for non-food products; packaging for dangerous products; individual packaging; collective packaging.
- g. by degree of rigidity: rigid packaging; semi-rigid packaging; light packaging.
- h. by way of packaging: reusable packaging; non-reusable packaging (lost type).
- i. by circulation system: packaging return system; system of sale - purchase of the packaging.
- j. by means of transport: packaging for land transport; packaging for river-maritime transport;
air transport packaging.
- k. by destination: packaging for the external market; packaging for the internal market.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

From a functional point of view, the packaging has the role of keeping the product safe, but also serves as a label for it. From a structural point of view, it consists of the actual packaging, made of cardboard, the bottle containing the fir syrup and the label on it. From an ergonomic point of view, the packaging has a special area to facilitate its transport. With the help of this hole, the consumer can use a single finger to hold the package in his hand. From an aesthetic-semantic point of view, the packaging starts from the image of a stylized fir cone, continuing with two strips that are fixed to each other and that represent the bending system for the consumer. The package has two windows, located parallel in the front and in the back, through which it is possible to view the bottle and its contents. The graphics on the packaging, but also on the bottle label represent the traditional motif "The fir's branch", stylized and reduced to a single color, compared to its initial version. This traditional motif originates from Bucovina, an area where the fir syrup is made every year.

The first packaging is one for fir syrup, created from the desire to promote traditional Romanian products, made at home, which do not contain chemicals and which offer a source of health. Fir syrup is made in spring or early summer from fir buds, sugar or honey and water. Fir syrup can be used for medicinal purposes, but it can also be a drink consumed in everyday life. On the Romanian market, fir syrup does not have many options from which one can choose from. The way in which the product is presented, the graphics and the connection between the product and the packaging fail to attract customers in a surprising way, the product being bought mostly by the ones who need it to boost their health. Therefore, the intention of the packaging I want to create is to attract customers to buy this product, regardless of their reasons for consumption.

Fig.1 Packaging silhouette - fir syrup (left) and unfolded packaging - fir syrup (right)
Graphic designer: Oana-Corina Ungureanu

Fig. 2. Logos for Ținutul Călimanilor. Graphic designer: Oana-Corina Ungureanu

The second example is the identity created for "Ținutul călimanilor", which includes the logo, the business card and the three-dimensional label for the products marketed by "Ținutul călimanilor". The visual aspect is simple, easy to remember, with a strong visual impact due to the contrast between black and white. Also, the dark color gives an elegant, unitary look. The symbol from the identity is extracted from the embroidery specific to Bucovina, the area where we find this producer.

CONCLUSIONS

Advertising is omnipresent in everyday life. We are exposed to hundreds, or even thousands of compelling visual messages every day. These messages always try to convince us to feel, to believe, to act, to buy and to change ourselves. They reach us all the time and this happens through various public or personal settings, both in the offline and online environment. Some of these visual messages manage to affect our attitude and behavior more than others and, most of

the time, without realizing it. The way in which we choose to promote our products is the key to success in sales. Each element of graphic design manages to influence the customer in his or her decision to buy the product.

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